

LOWER VOLUME FRACTION SiC_p/AL COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY SQUEEZE INFILTRATION CASTING

Kung-Hsien Shue and Su-Jien Lin

*Department of Materials Science and Engineering
National Tsing Hua University, Hsinchu, Taiwan, R.O.C.*

SUMMARY: The volume fraction of particulate reinforcement in an aluminum composite fabricated by squeeze infiltration casting is always about 50 vol% or higher. To make lower volume fraction composites (0-25 vol%), a mixed preform, composed of pure aluminum powder and SiC particles, was used and squeeze cast by a low melting-point alloy (AA383). Reinforcement macro-distribution uniformity and successful infiltration suggest that the suitable processing parameters are: melt temperature, 750°C; preform temperature, 515°C; infiltration pressure, 75 MPa; ram speed, 4 mm/s. Microstructure analysis shows that SiC_p distributed uniformly and no pore was observed for all the composites with various volume fraction or size of particulate reinforcement. The tensile properties of 85 μm SiC_p/Al/A383 composites (0-25 vol%) are better than that of A383 alloy though pure Al has a low strength. It is resulted from the refinement of silicon plates.

KEYWORDS: SiC_p/Al composites, squeeze casting, microstructures, tensile properties

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been developed and applied as structural materials in aerospace and automobile industry for two decades because of their high specific strength, high specific stiffness, good elevated temperature properties, and better wear resistance [1-4]. Among these composites, short fiber and particulate reinforced aluminum matrix composites have maintained a lot of emphases recently because of their isotropic properties. Methods for the production of the particulate reinforced MMCs mainly involve liquid casting [5,6] and powder metallurgy [7]. Though liquid casting offers an advantage of high economic profit, many defects, such as gas porosity, oxide inclusions, clustering of the reinforcements, and intensive interfacial reaction between the reinforcements and the molten metal, incorporate with this products and result in the worse properties [8]. In other side, the powder metallurgy method offers the products good properties, however, the cost is expensive.

Squeeze casting [9-11] eliminates the gas porosity and interfacial reaction by a large pressure and rapid solidification rate, respectively, offering a combination of economic profit and good properties. However, only the composites with high and fixed volume fraction of the reinforcements can be obtained by a traditional squeeze casting. In our research, a mixed preform, composed of the reinforcements and pure aluminum powders, lowered the amount of the reinforcements in the composites. Squeeze casting this mixed preform by a lower

melting-point aluminum alloy obtained the composites containing lower and various volume fraction of the reinforcements.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials

Four different particle size of SiC_p: 85 μm (180 mesh), 35 μm (400 mesh), 15 μm (800 mesh), and 12 μm (1200 mesh), with a density of 3.22 g/cm³ were chosen as the reinforcements. The 40 μm (325 mesh) commercial pure aluminum powders with the purity of 99.7% was mixed with SiC_p to lower the amount of reinforcements in the preform. The lower melting-point A383 Al alloy, whose solidus temperature is 515⁰C and liquidus temperature is 585⁰C, was chosen as the casting matrix material. The chemical composition of AA383 Al alloy was obtained by the inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometer (ICP-AES) analysis and was Al-8.60 wt% Si-2.28 wt% Cu-0.14 wt% Fe.

Preforms

Various volume fractions of the reinforcements were determined by the mixing ratio of the amount of SiC_p to that of the pure aluminum powder. The proper amounts of the different particle-size SiC_p and the aluminum powder were well ball mixed for one hour and then cold compacted at a pressure of 5 MPa to be the SiC_p/Al mixed preform. Another preform, pure aluminum without reinforcements, was also prepared for comparison.

Squeeze Castings

The SiC_p/Al preform was preheated in the mold to 465 or 515⁰C. Molten A383 alloy at 685 or 750⁰C was poured into the mold and followed by the push action of the preheated ram. The pressure between 50 and 125 MPa was applied to squeeze the liquid A383 alloy into the preform at various ram speeds between 1-6 mm/s until the ram could no longer advance. After squeeze casting, the SiC_p/Al/A383 composites containing different volume fraction and particle size of the reinforcements were furnace cooled and obtained. Monolithic A383 alloy and Al/A383 alloys without reinforcements were also squeeze cast and compared to the composites.

Microstructure Observations

Optical microscopy (OM) and JEOL scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) were applied to investigate the microstructure of composites and the distribution of reinforcements. Volume fraction of SiC_p was obtained by a LECO image analysis system. Specimens for OM and SEM observations were prepared by conventional metallographic procedures up to 0.05 μm diamond powder polishing. The fracture surface of the tensile test specimens were analyzed by SEM.

Tensile Tests

Tensile tests were conducted using a materials testing system (MTS 810). Before test, the specimens were machined to a gauge size of 6.25 mm in width, 3 mm in thickness, and a gauge length of 25 mm. The surfaces of the specimens were polished to 600 mesh.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Squeeze Castings

Table 1 The SiCp volume fractions of various locations in the 25 vol% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383 composites fabricated by various squeeze pressures and ram speeds at 515 °C preform and 750 °C melt temperatures.

Location from Bottom (mm)	2	10	17	Average	Standard
Location from Side (mm)	0~25, 25~50	0~25, 25~50	0~25, 25~50	Value	Deviation
50 MPa, 2 mm/s	incomplete infiltration				
75 MPa, 2 mm/s	27.66, 25.59	27.68, 32.43	25.65, 26.38	27.63	2.29
100 MPa, 2 mm/s	28.46, 24.99	28.82, 33.01	29.61, 29.02	28.98	2.34
125 MPa, 2 mm/s	26.90, 24.46	29.40, 31.91	27.76, 25.84	27.71	2.42
75 MPa, 1 mm/s	incomplete infiltration				
75 MPa, 3 mm/s	25.61, 23.30	28.80, 29.36	33.28, 28.20	28.09	3.11
75 MPa, 4 mm/s	26.25, 23.03	25.53, 26.33	24.84, 25.08	25.18	1.11
75 MPa, 5 mm/s	24.74, 23.08	30.47, 28.26	37.14, 29.91	28.93	4.53
75 MPa, 6 mm/s	30.15, 30.33	33.37, 29.78	38.06, 35.55	32.87	3.10

The 25 vol% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383 alloy composites were used to check the optimum squeeze casting parameters. The preform and melt temperatures of squeeze casting were selected at 515 and 750°C, respectively, because too low temperature resulted in an incomplete infiltration. Table 1 exhibits the SiCp volume percentages of various locations in the 25 vol% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383 composites fabricated under various squeeze pressures and ram speeds at 515°C preform and 750°C melt temperatures. Each datum is the average value of five 100x pictures of a location specimen. The infiltration was not complete when the squeeze pressure was only 50 MPa. The preform can be complete infiltrated as the squeeze pressure was increased to 75 MPa or more. The volume fraction and distribution uniformity of SiCp are almost the same for various squeeze pressure condition in the successful infiltrated composites. This means that the optimum squeeze pressure is 75 MPa from economic aspect.

For various ram speeds, Table 1 shows the optimum ram speed is 4 mm/s because it can result the most uniform distribution and the least volume percentage of SiCp. These suggest that the deformation of the preform under 4 mm/s ram speed is the smallest during squeeze casting processing. Darcy's law is usually used to describe a non-compressible fluid infiltrates the porous preform [12] and is

$$dP/dX = -(\mu/k)/V \quad (1)$$

where dP/dX is pressure gradient, μ is viscosity, k is permeability, and V is fluid velocity. Increasing ram speed increases the fluid velocity and decreases the fluid viscosity because the heat absorption by preform is increased. The former increases the pressure gradient, however, the latter decreases the pressure gradient. The degree of preform deformation is dependent on the pressure gradient. A higher pressure gradient will result in a severer deformation of preform. So that, to get a minimum distortion of preform and uniform SiCp distribution, a optimum ram speed should be selected. In this experiment, the optimum ram speed is 4 mm/s.

From above results, the suitable squeeze processing parameters are: 750°C melt temperature, 515 °C preform temperature, 75 MPa infiltration pressure, and 4 mm/s ram speed.

Microstructures

Fig. 1 Microstructures of the squeeze casting (a) A383 and (b) Al/A383 alloys.

Figure 1 shows the microstructures of the squeeze casting A383 and Al/A383 alloys. A large amount of silicon plates precipitated in the A383 Al alloy as shown in Fig. 1a. Several tens micrometers of the silicon plates grew up without any limitations and distributed randomly in the A383 Al alloy. However, in the squeeze cast Al/A383 alloy, as shown in Fig. 1b, the size of the silicon precipitates decreased to a few micrometers and the shape of precipitates in the Al/A383 alloy changed to smaller spheroids. Precipitation of silicon concentrated around different-size and round shape particles, that seems to be the added aluminum powders. It suggests that Al powders did not melt obviously during squeeze casting, but only the surfaces of powders melted and Al powders behaved as a limitation for the growth of the silicon precipitates. Besides, melting of the surfaces of aluminum powders needed to adsorb a lot of heat and would lower the temperature of the A383 alloy melt. This resulted in a rapid solidification rate and refined the size of silicon precipitates.

Figure 2 shows the microstructures of SiCp/Al/A383 composites with (a) 8 vol% 85 μm , (b) 14.5 vol% 85 μm , (c) 21 vol% 85 μm , and (d) 21 vol% 12 μm SiCp. The distributions of SiCp in the matrix are rather uniform and no pore can be found in all composites. These suggest that squeezing a low melting-point alloy (A383) into a mixed preform, composed of pure aluminum powder and SiC particles, is a successful technique to make lower volume fraction (0-25 vol%) composites. Figure 3 shows the microstructures of a squeeze cast SiCp/Al/A383 composite and Al/A383 alloy with higher magnification. It is easier to observe the size and shape of silicon precipitates. Many silicon precipitates nucleated heterogeneously on the SiCp and aluminum powders. Silicon were refined by the addition of SiCp and Al powder due to the growth limitation. However, the size and shape of silicon precipitates in SiCp/Al/A383 composites were not as small and round as that in Al/A383 alloys, as shown in Fig. 3. Adding SiCp, that is decreasing the amount of aluminum powders, reduces the quantity of heat adsorbed by the surface melting of aluminum powders, and results in the less refinement of the silicon precipitates.

Figure 2 The microstructures of SiCp/Al/A383 composites with (a) 8 vol% 85 μm , (b) 14.5 vol% 85 μm , (c) 21 vol% 85 μm , and (d) 21 vol% μm SiCp.

Fig. 3 Microstructures of the squeeze casting (a) 21 vol% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383 composite and (b) Al/A383 alloy.

Tensile Properties

Table 2 shows the tensile properties of the squeeze cast A383, pure Al/A383 alloys and various SiCp/Al/A383 composites. The tensile strengths of the A383 and Al/A383 alloys are 166 and 188 MPa, respectively. Though the strength of the pure Al is absolutely lower than the A383 alloy, the tensile strength of the Al/A383 alloy is higher than that of the A383 alloy

due to the refinement of the silicon precipitates. By the same reason, the elongation of the Al/A383 alloy increases to 12.2% from 0.65%, elongation of the A383 alloy. However, the yield strength and Young's modulus of Al/A383 alloy are lower than that of A383 alloy because of the existence of pure aluminum in Al/A383 alloy.

Table 2 Tensile properties of various squeeze cast specimens.

Specimens	Tensile Strength MPa	Yield Strength MPa	Young's Modulus GPa	Elongation %
A383	166	142	86	0.7
Al/A383	188	75	76	12.2
8% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383	180	77	88	7.6
15% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383	176	85	100	5.3
21% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383	174	105	112	3.6
25% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383	174	117	118	2.1
21% 12 μm SiCp/Al/A383	223	121	104	3.0

For the 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383 composites, the tensile strength and elongation decrease from 180 to 174 MPa and 7.6% to 2.1%, respectively, as the SiCp content increases from 8 to 25 vol% because the large stress concentration on SiCp results in the earlier failure of the composites. However, the yield strengths and Young's moduli of the composites arise by the addition of the rigid SiCp. The tensile strength and yield strength of composites can be increased to 223 MPa and 121 MPa, respectively, by changing SiCp size from 85 μm to 12 μm . These must be resulted from the plastic constrain and Si refinement by the fine SiCp.

Comparing the composites and A383 alloy, the tensile properties of composites are better than that of A383 alloy except the yield strength. The major reasons are the refinement of silicon and some low strength pure Al in the composites. As for the Al/A383 alloy, the largest elongation should be resulted from the strongest silicon refinement and lack of SiCp.

Fracture Surfaces

Figures 4 shows the fracture surfaces after tensile tests of the squeeze cast (a) A383, (b) Al/A383, (c) 25 vol% 85 μm SiCp/Al/A383, and (d) 21 vol% 12 μm SiCp/Al/A383 specimens. As shown in Fig. 4a, obvious cleavage of the silicon plates and aluminum matrix without dimples dominates the brittle fracture behavior of the A383 Al alloy. In contrast, little cleavage of the silicon precipitates on the fracture surface of the Al/A383 alloy, shown in Fig. 4b, are associated with a large amount of dimples and explains the better ductility. These fine dimples are resulted from the silicon refinement in the Al/A383 alloy.

From the fracture surfaces of the composites, cleavage and crash of the 85 μm SiCp always happens whether the amount of SiCp was 8 or 25 vol% (Fig. 4c). No decohesion in the interface reveals a good and strong bonding between SiCp and the matrix. Cleavage and crash of SiCp illustrates the large stress concentration on SiCp and results a decrease in tensile strength of composites with higher SiCp content. A larger amount of dimples was found in the composite containing 8 vol% of SiCp. Decreasing amount of dimples as increasing the SiCp content explains the decrease of the elongation. Figure 4d shows the fracture surface of the 21 vol% 12 μm SiCp/Al/A383 composite. Cleavage of the SiCp associating with a large amount of dimples in the matrix is the dominant fracture mode. Some SiCp pull-out was found in the 12 μm SiCp/ Al/A383 composite. Comparing composites with A383 alloy, the

dimple quantity on the fracture surface of composites is much more than that of A383 alloy because of the silicon refinement in composites. This can explain the tensile properties of composites are better than that of A383 alloy, especially for the 21 vol% 12 μm SiC_p/Al/A383 composite.

Figure 4 The fracture surfaces of the squeeze cast (a) A383, (b) Al/A383, (c) 25 vol% 85 μm SiC_p/Al/A383, and (d) 21 vol% 12 μm SiC_p/Al/A383 specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A special squeeze infiltration technique, using a lower melting point A383 Al alloy to infiltrate the Al/SiC_p mixed preform, has been developed to fabricate lower SiC_p volume fraction (0-25 vol%) metal matrix composites.
2. The suitable squeeze processing parameters are: 750°C melt temperature, 515°C preform temperature, 75 MPa infiltration pressure, and 4 mm/s ram speed.
3. SiC_p distributed uniformly and no pore was observed for all the composites with various volume fraction or size of particulate reinforcement.
4. The tensile properties of SiC_p/Al/A383 composites (0-25 vol%) are better than that of A383 alloy though pure Al has a low strength, especially for the 12 μm SiC_p composite. This is resulted from the refinement of silicon plates.

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